

An Analysis of Teachers' Pedagogical/Professional Learning a Practice Competence in Teaching English at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti

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ABSTRACT

This research uses a descriptive qualitative method as a research methodology. This research was conducted to determine Teacher Pedagogic Competence/Professional Learning Practices in English Language Learning based on the Directorate General of GTK, Ministry of Education and Culture Number 6565/B/GT/2020. The population and sample in this study were all 3 teachers at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti. Data collection methods used in this study were questionnaires and interviews. The results showed that teachers' perceptions of Teacher Pedagogic Competence/Professional Learning Practices in English Language Learning based on the Director General of GTK of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 6565/B/GT/2020 at Baranti 4 Public Middle School received a response with the presentation results on indicators of developing a classroom environment that facilitates student learning by safe and comfortable shows results of 3 (100%) in the average category, on design indicators shows results (100%) average category, indicators assess, provide input, and send learning reports show results of 1 (33%) in the medium category, 2 (67%) in the bad category, and on indicators that involve parents/guardians and the community in learning shows results 3 (100%) in the poor category.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and also planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop the potential that exists in themselves to have religious spiritual power, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, as well as the skills needed by themselves, society, Thus, education is needed and very important in life to form a personality rather than a person either in a formal environment or a non-formal environment. One of the competencies that determine success in the learning process Pedagogic competence is very important in a process learning because it is directly related to how the teacher transfer knowledge with students. Teachers' pedagogical competence is the ability to manage learning, which includes planning, implementation and evaluation of learning outcome of learners. These competencies should be owned by every teacher in order to achieve success in learning and teaching (Baker, EL, 2005). One of the challenges the teachers face is the fulfillment of their potential. It is believe that many teachers fail to fulfill potential, not because of they do not know the subject matter, but because they do not understand students or classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Another opinion about pedagogical competence of teacher is from Istarani (2015) who state that in pedagogical competence, a teacher at least has to understand the goal of teaching, the manner of formulating the goal of teaching, in particular choosing and deciding the teaching method in correspond with the desire result, understanding the learning material as good as possible by using various source, the manner of choosing, deciding and using props, the manner of making a test and its usage, and knowledge about other evaluation devices. The teacher may be called as a competent teacher if they have a good competence. It is because of both of them are two important factors EFL teacher need to conducting successful classroom instruction (Brown, 2001). Therefore, the study of teachers' competence and performance in language teaching has become an important aspect of effective teaching in every school. It is stated in the Perdirjen GTK Kemendikbud Ristek Number 6565 / B / GT / 2020 Concerning Competency Models in Teacher Professional Development, that teachers must carry out professional development in order to improve their professionalism at least through: education; and/or education and training.

It was emphasized in the Perdirjen GTK Kemendikbud Research and Technology Number 6565 / B / GT / 2020 Concerning Competency Models in Teacher Professional Development, that the Competency Model consists of: teacher competency models and school leadership competency models. The teacher competency model includes the categories: a) professional knowledge; b) professional learning practice ; and c) professional development

From the observations did at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti, in providing learning materials, teachers still lack literature resources, tend to struggle with passive, unidirectional, monotonous learning patterns, and do not use varied learning methods. Although variations of learning methods are found, the purpose of utilization and placement is often unknown. From the explanation

above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title An Analysis of teachers' pedagogical/ Professional Learning Practice competence in teaching English at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti.

METHODS

(Creswell, 2014) explained "Research design are the specific procedure involved in the research process: data collection, data analysis, and report writing". The research design in this research uses analysis research design. This research uses descriptive qualitative method because the data is described using words or sentences to analyze which is teachers' pedagogical competence in teaching english . (Creswell, 2014) Qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem . The researcher builds a complex,holistic picture,analyzes natural setting,words,report detailed views of information, and conducts the study in a natural setting. Researcher want to observe and describe teachers' pedagogical/proffesional learning practice competence in teaching english at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti .

Setting and Subject of the Research

This research will be conduct at the English teacher of SMP Negeri 4 Baranti. Researcher chose this school because researcher found several problems in teaching English. In addition, Researcher want to know the teaching and learning process and patterns of interaction that occur between teachers and students in a learning class either directly or indirectly through this research. The subjects of this study is teachers.Consisting of 3 teacher. Researcher analyzed teachers pedagogical/proffesional learning practice competence in teaching english.

Interview

Interview is a data collection technique by ask questions to respondents and record or record respondents' answers. In conducting interviews in order to avoid things that are not become the focus of research is to interview sources data or subjects who have direct knowledge and experience to the problem being researched.

Techniques for analyzing questionnaire data about the application of teacher competence in the learning process in this study, the first step is to provide a score, where the maximum score is equal to 4 and the minimum score is equal to 1. The scoring of the questions or statements is as follows:

Table. 1 The Scoring of the Questions

No.	Category	Code	Score
1	Proficient/ Always	M	4
2	Talking/Frequently	C	3
3	Worth / Sometimes	L	2
4	Developing/ Never	B	1

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Questionnaire

Sum of questionnaires on teacher pedagogical /professional learning practices competence. In analyzing the questionnaire, the researcher counted in each statement the total number of respondents who answered each category divided by the number of respondents.

Development of a Classroom Environment that Facilitates Student Learning Safely and Comfortably

From the results of the researcher's calculations, which were measured by 8 questions to 3 english teacher. The distribution table of the research results on the statement on teacher pedagogical /professional learning practices competence in teaching English can be categorized as follows:

Table. 2 Classification Score Development of a Classroom Environment that Facilitates Student Learning Safely and Comfortably

Classification	Score	Frequency	Percent (%)
Excelent	81-100	0	0
Very Good	61 - 80	0	0
Good	41 - 60	0	0
Average	21 - 40	3	100
Poor	0 - 20	0	0
Total		3	100

Figure 1. Classification Score

Design, Application, and Reflection of Effective Learning

From the results of the researcher's calculations, which were measured by 8 questions to 3 English teacher. The distribution table of the research results on the statement on teacher pedagogical /professional learning practices competence in teaching English can be categorized as follows:

Table. 3 Classification Score Design, Application, and Reflection of Effective Learning

Classification	Score	Frequency	Percent (%)
Excelent	81-100	0	0
Very Good	61 - 80	0	0
Good	41 - 60	0	0
Average	21 - 40	3	100
Poor	0 - 20	0	0
Total		3	100

Figure. 2 Classification Score

Assesment, Feed, and Submit Learning Reports

From the results of the researcher's calculations, which were measured by 8 questions to 3 english teacher. The distribution table of the research results on the statement on teacher pedagogical /professional learning practices competence in teaching English can be categorized as follows:

Figure. 3 The Distribution Table

Involve Parents/Guardians and the Community in Learning

From the results of the researcher's calculations, which were measured by 6 questions to 3 english teacher. The distribution table of the research results on the statement on teacher pedagogical /professional learning practices competence in teaching English can be categorized as follows:

Table. 4 Classification Score Involve Parents/Guardians and the Community in Learning

Classification	Score	Frequency	Percent (%)
Excelent	81 – 100	0	0
Very Good	61 – 80	0	0
Good	41 – 60	0	0
Average	21 – 40	0	0
Poor	0 – 20	3	100
Total		3	100

Figure. 4 Classification Score Involve Parents

Based on the data above, 3 (100%) English teachers' are classified as poor. No teachers were classified as Excellent, Very good, Good and Average. The following is a discussion of the results of the questionnaire and interviews with English teachers that describe how the teachers' pedagogical/professional learning practice competence in teaching English at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti.

Development of a Classroom Environment that Facilitates Student Learning Safely and Comfortably

The results of the questionnaire show that the 3 English teachers have an average ability in Developing a Classroom Environment that Facilitates Student Learning Safely and Comfortably. Then, based on the results of interviews with the English teacher at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti, they first made an agreement with the students and took part in managing the classroom and giving students the opportunity to be able to share together. these efforts are made to develop a classroom environment that facilitates student learning safely and comfortably.

According to Nurjana (2021) Efforts to build a positive culture in schools that are pro-students begin with forming an environmental class that supports the creation of a positive culture, namely by compiling a class agreement. Effective classroom agreements can help in the formation of a positive discipline culture in the classroom. This can also help make the teaching and learning process easier and less stressful. Often with student problems related to communication between students and teachers, especially when students prohibit a rule on the grounds that they do not know the rule exists. The class agreement contains several rules to help teachers and students work together to form effective teaching and learning activities. The class agreement contains not only the teacher's expectations for students, but also the students' expectations for the teacher. Agreements are drawn up and developed jointly between teachers and students.

Design, Application, and Reflection of Effective Learning

The results of the questionnaire show that the 3 English teachers have an average ability in Design, Application, and Reflection of Effective Learning.

According to the answer of respondents all about Design, Application, and Reflection of Effective Learning, every teacher certainly has a plan in starting or planning. There are a few points first, looking at syllabus to find out what material teaching, then look at the education calendar to adjust what material and how many meetings are held in 1 semester. And the third is making lesson plans according to the syllabus. To reveal it, is the same as reassessing the RPP that has been made, it might improve. There may be something that must be removed in the RPP, such as adding or subtracting.

The teacher tries to modify the curriculum to the specific needs of the school. According to Reinesa Noor Emilasari (2010) in her research, "An Analysis of Teachers' Pedagogical Competence in Lesson Study of MGMP SMP Majalengka one of the Indonesian government's efforts in improving teacher professionalism and quality of education is by adopting the concept of Lesson Study from Japan. Lesson Study is an ongoing professional development process of improving a lesson through teacher collaboration. Lesson Study involves a group of teachers meeting regularly to work on the design, implementation, testing, and improvement of one or several research lessons that are: teacher's problem, goal or vision of pedagogical practice, observing, analyzing / reflecting, and discussing.

According to Agus (2021) One part of the lesson plan that is very important to be made by the teacher as a learning guide is the Syllabus and Learning Implementation Plan (RPP). The syllabus explains the objectives that must be achieved to achieve educational goals and the procedures to be used. Not only that, the syllabus also contains an evaluation method used to test the level of educational success. The syllabus is a set of plans and arrangements for educational activities, class management and assessment of learning outcomes (Nurdiana, 2017). Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) is a more specific planning tool than a syllabus. This learning implementation plan is designed to guide teachers in teaching so that they are not far from learning objectives. Recognizing the importance of planning these lessons, program teachers don't teach without planning.

Assesment, provide input, and send Learning Reports

The results of the questionnaire show that the 1 out of 3 English teachers have an average ability in assessments, provide input, and send learning reports. Then, based on the results of interviews with the English teacher at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti the assessment consists of 2, namely practical and written. And for assessment also how do students collaborate with friends to solve a problem. written assessment and practice are found in PTS, PAS, and PAT. For students who have less grades are given a kind of repetition (Remedial).

According to Nur Aisyah Dangka Bulawan (2019) Urgensi Evaluasi Pembelajaran Dalam Proses Belajar Mengajar PAI di SMAN 2 Luwu, evaluation to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process usually teachers carry out various evaluation activities, with evaluation techniques used such as giving oral questions both before lessons, mid-lesson, and the end

of lessons . But evaluations are also given in the form of daily tests , practices , and assignments . To encourage students interest and focus in learning.

Involve Parents/Guardians and the Community in Learning

The results of the questionnaire show that the 3 English teachers have an less ability in involve parents/guardians and the Community in Learning. Based on the interview with the English teachers , the role of parents in educating children is very important because it is also their biggest responsibility. The role of parents in educating children involves more than just providing a sense of security and confidence. Perhaps many parents mistakenly believe that their children's education is entirely in the hands of teachers. Because in truth, a child's first education starts from home. Efforts made include communicating with parents of students through the media to convey what obstacles students experience while studying, providing information to parents to guide and remind their children in matters related to the learning process.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion above on the teachers' pedagogical/professional learning practice competence in teaching English at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti, the researchers conclude as follows At SMP Negeri 4 Baranti, the teachers' pedagogical/professional learning practice based on the regulations of the directorate general of the ministry of education and culture number 6565/B/GT/ 2020 skill in teaching English was good/average. The teachers' interview response revealed that the teacher has implemented the principle of pedagogical/professional learning practice competence in the learning process.

The good/average category in teaching English is found in the results of the questionnaire. Based on the Director General of the Ministry of Education and Culture number 6565/B/GT/2020, the indicator for developing a classroom environment that facilitates student learning safely and comfortably shows results of 3 (100%) in the average category, on the design indicator, shows results (100%) the average category, the indicators for assessing, providing input, and sending learning reports show results 1 (33%) in the average category, 2 (67%) in the bad category, and on indicators that involve parents/guardians and the community in learning show results 3 (100%) in the poor category

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on the topic "An Analysis of Teachers' Pedagogical/ Professional Learning a Practice Competence in Teaching English at SMP Negeri 4 Baranti."

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